

EVALUATION OF THE HYGROTHERMAL BEHAVIOR OF A FULL-SCALE ADOBE EVAPORATIVE COOLER

Camila Catherine de Morais Cassundé, Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul, BRA,
camila.cassunde@ufms.br

Thainara de Araújo, Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul, BRA, thainara.de.araujo@gmail.com

Andrea Naguissa Yuba, Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul, BRA, naguissa.yuba@ufms.br

João Onofre Pereira Pinto, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, EUA, pintoj@ornl.gov

ABSTRACT

A full-scale adobe-based evaporative cooler was built to be low-cost, and eco-friendly cooling storage for fruits and vegetables in vulnerable communities in developing countries. This paper evaluated the thermal behavior of the cooler, by measuring real-time conditions of temperature and humidity under different circumstances of water irrigation in 12 weeks during the dry season in Campo Grande, MS, Brazil. Disregarding other variables (solar radiance and wind), the cooler without irrigation had a similar temperature loss but lower efficiency due to intrinsic evaporative cooling behavior of adobe. Results show the system can contribute to decreasing internal temperature even without water input.

KEYWORDS

Evaporative cooling; Sustainability; Thermal efficiency; Adobe; earthen building.

INTRODUCTION

Several communities in emerging countries, whose main source of subsistence is family farming, don't have appropriate storage for production, which is a problem considered global and difficult to solve and it is strongly linked to the climate changes suffered in recent years. Consequently, technological alternatives with reduced cost and energy consumption for a sustainable agriculture are necessary. These solutions value these populations and provide improvements in their quality of life, looking for a way to reduce hunger, achieve better food security and nutrition. The worst future scenario demands a new type of development to meet the needs of this still growing population, especially where there is scarcity of fertile lands due to urban expansion and adverse conditions (Mossin et al., 2018). For such places, the storage of food for a longer time and the reduction of losses achieved by an evaporative cooling system can benefit several communities around the world without access to electricity. (Abano et al., 2011; Ambuko et al., 2017; Islam et al., 2012)

Evaporative cooling is one of the oldest and most efficient ways to passively cool buildings in dry climates, and it is also used as a storage method for fruits and vegetables around the world. Watt (1963) performed the first rigorous analysis of direct and indirect evaporative systems, and his works were the beginning of scientific research about evaporative cooling. Its use for food preservation can extend the shelf life of agricultural productions in remote or vulnerable locations and can contribute to income generation and to decrease postharvest losses caused by inadequate storage until commercially traded. Especially in tropical countries, due to their high humidity, fruits and vegetables have a short shelf life and are susceptible to rotting quickly (Lal Basediya et al., 2013). But despite using relatively simple technology, they are still rarely used in these regions, such as Brazil (Camargo, 2003).

Ambuko (2017), Islam (2012), Albano (2011), have currently developed studies on the conservation of post-harvest vegetables in evaporative cooling chambers. They see evaporative cooling as a low-cost

alternative for small communities that do not have access to electrically powered cooling equipment, as all studies concluded that the temperature is significantly lower, depending on the technology used in the cooler. The physical behavior of evaporative cooling is based on the evaporation of water that removes heat from the environment or material in a natural way and the faster it happens, the greater the temperature drop, as the working fluids are air and water, and it is more efficient when temperatures are high and humidity is low. The water is vaporized within the air stream and the heat and mass exchanged between air and water reduce the dry bulb temperature of the air and increase its humidity, keeping the enthalpy (adiabatic cooling) constant. Albano (2011) obtained a temperature loss between 6 and 9°C, since it uses simpler materials and Islam (2014), who builds a version with different types of aggregated technologies, achieved 20°C at some points. In both studies, the relative humidity is high and the temperature difference is around 7°C. Camargo (2003) obtained results that showed the variation of average dry bulb temperatures during the day (8 am to 6 pm) of up to 7.4°C. Rempel R. and Rempel W. (2016) indicate a potential for hygroscopic earthen buildings to cool themselves by evaporation through sorption of moisture from humid night air and evaporation during warm weather the next day, thus reducing necessity of water input in evaporative cooling systems which is beneficial for water-scarce regions. Other recent experiments conducted by Liu, Lyu, et al. (2017) performed the computational analysis of the thermal environment in an evaporative cooler built in ceramic bricks with a pad of a mixture of sand and zeolite, which removes heat energy from the air and generates a significant temperature difference, proving that the results found empirically are compatible with those found in their simulations.

In this experiment, the evaporative cooler was built with handcrafted adobe bricks using red-yellow latosol found locally and stabilized with cement in proportion 12:1 for the double-wall and sand for the filling. This type of soil contains sand, silt and clay, and it is found to be not fictile and compressible (Pacheco & Dias Junior, 1990). Earth building materials are mainly hygroscopic, absorbing and releasing moisture and transferring associated heat according to their physical properties and they are also among the lowest available in terms of environmental impact. (Rempel & Rempel, 2016). Also, due to the physical characteristics of the adobe and the sand as porous ceramic materials, it makes them suitable for indirect evaporative cooling, once it has high porosity, high hydrophilicity surface, high thermal conductivity and high water resistance. Neville (1997) points out that swelling is the increase in volume of a mass of sand, due to water films, displacing the particles in order to separate them. Considering that completely dry sand is used, when being put in contact with water, its empty pores will be filled and part of the water won't be evaporated right away. These parameters contribute to increasing the contact time between the flowing air and the water film, increasing the enthalpy and, consequently, the temperature drop (Lv et al., 2021). The thermal stability is typically attributed to the thermal inertia of the earth's massive material and has suggested that intrinsic evaporative cooling contributes significantly to the thermal comfort of adobe buildings, compensating for eventual sensible heat gain due to the thermal behavior of earthen materials (Rempel & Rempel, 2016).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental site

This project was conducted to determine the potentials and limitations of the system. A full-scale adobe zero-energy cool chamber called “Resfriador do Cerrado” (or Cerrado cooler) was built. Actual time conditions of temperature and humidity under different circumstances of water irrigation were measured. The experimental time was about 12 weeks during the dry season in Campo Grande, Mato Grosso do Sul State, taking three weeks for each of the four conditions studied: no water, 100L of water daily, 200L of water daily and 400L of water daily. The observations were made at once a day during the experiment and the results were compared to the local meteorological station, while calculations of atmospheric pressure and enthalpy were calculated according to ASHRAE (2005). The saturation efficiency of the cooling system was calculated based on Riangvilaikul (2010).

Structure of the cerrado cooler

The cooler was built with earthen bricks (adobe), sand, metal roofing, metallic chimney, and a wood door, aiming to reduce cost and be able to be replicated in other vulnerable communities. As shown in

Figure 1 (a and b), the bricks were arranged to make a double wall measuring 450 x 450 cm and 380cm high, semi-buried 80cm from the ground level. 8m³ of construction sand was sandwiched between the two walls as an evaporating medium. Tap water is dripping over the sand to wet the filler material through a programmable flow valve (BWT20) connected to the water source. It has a storage space of 4,50m² and 17,1m³ of volume. It was covered with a metallic roofing with a zenith opening chimney. Also it was installed a slim wood structure inside and adobe buttresses outside to structure the walls.

a) Photo of the full-scale adobe evaporative cooler

b) Section of the full-scale adobe evaporative cooler

Figure 1: Full-scale adobe evaporative cooler

Data collection of temperature, relative humidity and watering

All temperatures and relative humidity were measured simultaneously in three different places inside the cooler. The first sensor was placed at ground level (0m high), the second one at a 1m high and the third one at a 2,5m high, coinciding with the end of the walls. For external temperatures, all data was collected from the local meteorological substation from INMET (Brazilian national meteorological institute). All data inside the cooler was measured using digital thermo hygrometers with data logger functions (HOBO U12-001 and TESTO 176 T2) both with accuracy $\pm 0,2$ °C and measuring range of -100 to +400 °C. The data was sampled at one-hour intervals for 21 days for each condition, totalizing 84 days. The watering of the internal layer of the cooler's walls was distributed from a water supply equally in drip nozzles through a programmable flow valve (BWT20) with an average error of 1s/24h. The watering rate was 2,5l/min distributed equally throughout the four walls.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Performance of the cooler

The overall performance regarding temperature and relative humidity inside the cooler was tested. Other variables (for instance solar radiance, wind, and others) were not considered during the analysis and the results may vary due to local microclimate where the cooler was built. The first situation investigated was the performance of the cooler without the use of water on the evaporative pad. First an statistical analysis of the data was made. Figure 2a represents all the temperature data collected for the period, showing constancy in data with few outliers below the minimum temperature and is positioned with the median around 20°C for all the situations. Most of the data inside the evaporative cooler show an interquartile range of 14°C and a positive data asymmetry. It is also visible that the outside temperature data have more significant variability than the ones inside the cooler, with an interquartile range of 26°C. Figure 2b represents all the relative humidity data collected for the period, showing a constancy in data with few outliers above the maximum and below minimum RH and it shows a difference between the medians of internal and external humidity. Most of the data inside the evaporative cooler show an interquartile range of 45% and symmetry. It is also visible that the outside temperature data have more significant variability than those inside the cooler, with an interquartile range of 80% and most of its data with values below the ones inside the cooler in all three situations.

a) Temperature data without water

b) RH data without water

Figure 2: Temperature and relative humidity data from experiment without watering

The following data was interpreted from a day within the main quartile from the boxplot graphs of the period. An increase in outside temperature is noticed by 9 am, having its peak at 3 pm and remaining high until 9 pm when it starts to decrease (Figure 3a). This increase also raises the temperature inside the cooler, but with a smooth curve that remains practically constant throughout the day. The dry bulb temperature inside the cooler is -7.9°C below the average outside temperature in this condition, with a difference/surplus of 15% of humidity, due to the cooling effects of the intrinsic evaporative cooling behavior of the adobe building. During a typical day there are oscillations of relative humidity. While there is a decrease between 11am and 9pm outside, the relative humidity inside the cooler remains higher than outside with less decrease during the day (Figure 3b). As the outside temperature increases, so does the evaporation rate from the double walls made in adobe with sand filling, decreasing the temperature inside the cooler. During this experiment atmospheric pressure was calculated at 0,94bar, wet bulb temperature of $17,47^{\circ}\text{C}$ and enthalpy of 51,61kJ/kg.

So:
$$\mathcal{E} = [(31,8^{\circ}\text{C} - 20,9^{\circ}\text{C}) / (31,8^{\circ}\text{C} - 16,18^{\circ}\text{C})] * 100$$

$$\mathcal{E}(100) = 69,78\%$$

The third experiment consisted in watering 200l daily, considering that the filling sand layer was watered for 1h20min, starting at 2 pm when the outside temperature was at its peak. In this scenario, there was an increase of constancy in temperature in comparison to the other situations (Figure 6a), with few outliers above the range. It is positioned with the median of the outside temperature above the others with a positive asymmetry of the data. Most of the measurements inside the evaporative cooler show an interquartile range of 9°C to 12°C and a symmetry of the data. For the outside data the interquartile range is 25°C, showing bigger variability. Figure 6b represents all the relative humidity data collected for the period, showing a lower constancy in data with more outliers above the maximum and below minimum RH than measured in the first two experiments and it shows the biggest difference between the medians of internal and external humidities in all of them. Most of the data inside the evaporative cooler show an interquartile range of 42% and 32% and a negative asymmetry of the data inside the cooler. It is also visible that the outside temperature data have greater variability than the ones inside the cooler, with an interquartile range of 70% with a positive asymmetry with most of its data with values below the ones inside the cooler and bigger distribution tails.

a) Temperature data with 200L/daily

b) RH data with 200L/daily

Figure 6: Temperature and relative humidity data from experiment with watering 200L/daily

The data from a day within the main quartile from the boxplot graphs of the period is shown in Figure 7a, where is observed that the outside temperature had the same pattern of oscillation when compared to the experiment of 100l/daily, with a difference of -8.19°C between the external and internal temperature. During this experiment atmospheric pressure was calculated at 0,94bar, wet bulb temperature of 16,06°C and enthalpy of 47,20kJ/kg. Although the temperature gain was very similar to the second situation, doubling the water significantly affected relative humidity, showing an increase of 29,87% inside the cooler. Figure 7b demonstrates a day with low relative humidity outside when the increase of the interior humidity was almost 60% at its peak, attesting that the effects of evaporation are amplified when facing drier climates. These results indicate a good response to the adobe cooling chamber in different geographical locations, such as the African continent, which has many vulnerable communities without access to electric energy but has a climate hot and dry enough to maximize the efficacy of the cooler.

a) Temperature in a day with 200L/daily

b) RH in a day with 200L/daily

Figure 7: Temperature and RH behavior from experiment with watering 200L/daily

If: $DBT_o = 31,2^{\circ}\text{C}$;

$DBT_i = 19,7^{\circ}\text{C}$;

$WBT_o = 16,06^{\circ}\text{C}$

$$\mathcal{E} = [(DBT_o - DBT_i)/(DBT_o - WBT_o)] * 100$$

So: $\mathcal{E} = [(31,2^{\circ}\text{C} - 19,7^{\circ}\text{C}) / (31,2^{\circ}\text{C} - 16,72^{\circ}\text{C})] * 100$

$$\mathcal{E}(200) = 79,41\%$$

The last situation explored was once again doubling the watering, achieving 400l daily, ending the first cycle of experiments in this study. The filling sand layer was watered constantly through a programmable flow valve (BWT20) in drip nozzles for approximately 2h40min starting at 2 pm when the outside temperature was at its peak. According to figure 8a, there was a constancy in data with few outliers above the range. It is positioned with the median of the outside temperature above the others in a symmetric way of data. Most of the findings inside the evaporative cooler show an interquartile range of 8°C to 10°C and a symmetry of the data. For the outside measurements, the interquartile range is 22°C, showing bigger variability and with positive asymmetry. The data reported in Figure 8b represents all the relative humidity data collected for the period, showing a lower constancy in measurements with more outliers above the maximum and below minimum RH and it shows a bigger difference between the medians of internal and external humidities than the first two experiments, but lower than the third one. Most of the measurements inside the evaporative cooler show an interquartile range of 48% and 40% and a symmetry of the data inside the cooler. It is also visible that the outside temperature data have the greatest variability in all experiments, with an interquartile range of 89% with a positive asymmetry with most of its values below the ones inside the cooler and the bigger distribution tail.

a) Temperature in a day with 400L/daily

b) RH in a day with 400L/daily

Figure 8: Temperature data from experiment with watering 400L/daily

The data from a day within the main quartile from the boxplot graphs of the period is shown in Figure 9a, where once again the average gain of temperature was similar to the preceding events, with a 9,12°C difference between the internal and external temperatures. However, the difference of 13,2°C was measured during a typical day. During this experiment atmospheric pressure was calculated of 0,94bar, wet bulb temperature of 17,43°C and enthalpy of 51,48kJ/kg. With lower humidity during this period, the average internal RH was 30,31% higher than external, but it reached a gain of 63,3% some nights around 20pm, as observed in Figure 9b. As a direct evaporative cooling system, the heat and the mass transfer through the air with water decreases the dry-bulb temperature, increasing the humidity and keeping the constant enthalpy characteristic of adiabatic cooling.

a) Temperature in a day with 400L/daily

b) RH in a day with 400L/daily

Figure 9: Temperature behavior from experiment with watering 400L/daily

If: $DBT_o = 35,5^{\circ}C$;

$DBT_i = 23,4^{\circ}C$;

$WBT_o = 17,43^{\circ}C$

$$\mathcal{E} = [(DBT_o - DBT_i)/(DBT_o - WBT_o)]*100$$

So: $\mathcal{E} = [(35,5^{\circ}C - 23,4^{\circ}C)/(35,5^{\circ}C - 17,43^{\circ}C)]*100$

$\mathcal{E}(400) = 66,96\%$

Making an analysis of the variance of the efficiencies reached in all experiments, based on the variables involved (such as external temperature, relative humidity, internal temperature and enthalpy) it was expected an increase of the saturation efficiency compatible with the increase of the water input, but considering the decrease of the efficiency in the 400L experiment, along with the low enthalpy, it is possible that the environment lacked water to achieve its best behavior, considering that the other variables were favorable.

Comparing the saturation efficiency of the adobe evaporative cooler with similar ones found in the literature (Table 1) it could reach similar results despite being a full-scale building located open-air and with a lower outside temperature.

Table 1: Comparison between evaporative coolers

Cooler	volume (m ³)	saturation efficiency (E)	temperature gain (°C)
Clay Evaporative Cooling ¹	0,23	20% - 90%	10°C
Evaporative cooler for sweet potatoes storage ²	0,27	87,17%	10,3°C
Evaporative Cooler (EVC) ³	not informed	17,3% - 98,8%	0,6°C - 18,3°C
Evaporative Cooling Barn ⁴	18,81	127%	6.5°C
Adobe Evaporative Cooler	17,1	57% - 79,41%	7,9°C - 9,16°C

Source: Adapted from (1) Ndukwu (2011), (2) Seweh et al. (2016), (3) Ndukwu e Manuwa (2015), (4) Abano et al. (2011).

CONCLUSION

The evaporative cooler can maintain lower inside temperature and higher inside relative humidity compared to outside temperature in all circumstances, even without watering. The experiment revealed that the temperature gain (external temperature - internal temperature) increased as the external temperature increased, showing an internal temperature almost stable despite the external temperature variation, but bigger saturation efficiency when the temperature is high and the relative humidity is low. It was also visible that the enthalpy had low variability comparing all four experiments, showing a bigger percentage of water evaporated than absorbed in the sand pad because when the enthalpy has a low variability, it is estimated that most of the molecules in the system are in their gas state. The cerrado cooler reached a temperature difference of 9,16°C when operating with 100L/daily and best saturation efficiency of 79,41% when operating with 200L/daily, having a compatible result compared with other authors., The dry bulb temperature inside of the cooler is -9.16°C below the average outside temperature with an addition of 16.69% of relative humidity when operating with 100L of water daily, -8.19°C and +29,87% when using 200L daily and -9,12°C and +30,31% with 400L daily. Even without water it shows an inner temperature -7.9°C below external temperature and almost 15% of additional humidity. When comparing the results from the cerrado cooler with other similar papers, it reaches a similar temperature difference and relative humidity gain, using fewer technology and viable materials.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abano, E. E., Teye, E., Amoah, R. S., & Tetteh, J. P. (2011). Design, Construction and Testing of an Evaporative cooling barn for Storing Sweet Potatoes in the Tropics. In *Asian Journal of Agricultural Research* (Vol. 5, Issue 2, pp. 115–126).
<https://doi.org/10.3923/ajar.2011.115.126>
- Ambuko, J., Wanjiru, F., Chemining'wa, G. N., Owino, W. O., & Mwachoni, E. (2017). Preservation of Postharvest Quality of Leafy Amaranth (*Amaranthus* spp.) Vegetables Using Evaporative Cooling. *Journal of Food Quality*, 2017, 1–7.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/5303156>
- Camargo, J. R. (2003). Resfriamento evaporativo: poupando a energia e o meio ambiente. *Revista Ciências Exatas*, 9/10(1–2), 69–75.
http://www.unitau.br/scripts/prppg/exatas/downloads/v_9_10/069.pdf
- Islam, M. P., Morimoto, T., & Hatou, K. (2012). Storage behavior of tomato inside a zero energy cool chamber. *Agricultural Engineering International: CIGR Journal*, 14(4), 209–217.
- Lal Basediya, A., Samuel, D. V. K., & Beera, V. (2013). Evaporative cooling system for storage of fruits and vegetables - A review. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 50(3), 429–442. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13197-011-0311-6>
- Lv, J., Xu, H., Zhu, M., Dai, Y., Liu, H., & Li, Z. (2021). The performance and model of porous materials in the indirect evaporative cooling system: A review. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 41(January), 102741. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobbe.2021.102741>
- Mossin, N., Stilling, S., Bøjstrup, T. C., Larsen, V. G., Lotz, M., & Blegvad, A. (2018). *An Architectural Guide to the UN 17 Sustainable Development Goals*. 158.
<https://adk.elsevierpure.com/en/publications/an-architecture-guide-to-the-un-17-sustainable-development-goals>
- Neville, A. M., Translation Giamusso S. E.; *Propriedades do concreto*. 2a ed, São Paulo: Pini, 1997, 824p.
- Pacheco, A. A. R. C. & Dias Junior, M. S. Estudo comparativo de métodos de campo e laboratório aplicados à confecção de blocos em adobe. [S.l.: s.n.], 1990. 14 p.
- Rempel, A. R., & Rempel, A. W. (2016). Intrinsic evaporative cooling by hygroscopic earth materials. In *Geosciences (Switzerland)* (Vol. 6, Issue 3).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences6030038>

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.